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EduPark: Real-time smart parking educational system

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ABSTRACT

A real-time physical and virtual model of smart parking system is developed to teach and compare physical system implementation with its virtual simulation. Developed parking system has one entrance and exit point, six parking spots and digital display, which shows number of free parking lots. Ultrasonic sensors are used for car identification on parking lots. As a main platform Arduino is used. All events from the parking are send to the remote database for further data analysis and data visualization to end-users. This system can be used by students to understand sensor operations, various development platform operation and programming tools and methods. Training can be given on different parking operation scenarios and algorithms.

Conference Key Areas: Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Sustainability and Engineering Education, Physics and Engineering Education

Keywords: Smart parking, parking simulation, engineering education

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INTRODUCTION

Real-time systems are used in various application areas [1], like production process control, agile manufacturing, medical applications and others. Smart city concept implementation includes real-time intelligent transport systems and parking systems.

Education of different aspects of real-time systems, using physical system experience is a valuable approach, but it is usually connected with different limitations, like expensiveness of equipment, safety concerns, etc [2]–[4]. Therefore, usually computer modelling and simulations replace real physical environment during education and prototyping. There are many advantages (low costs, instant availability, no limitations, fast implementation, no afraid of making mistakes) and disadvantages (possible lost sense of reality and limited creativity in generation of realistic system's perturbations) of process virtualization.

Good alternative is to substitute real full-scale physical system with its minimized prototype, which is implemented using the same technologies, methods and equipment, including sensors. This approach has following advantages: (1) gives impression of consequences in case of control failure, (2) demonstrates process fragility and low repeatability and (3) allows separation of the controlled process and computer-driven control process [3].

Authors of this paper developed physical model of real-time smart parking educational (experimental) system, together with its computer simulation. This approach joins modelling and physical world and can be used for wide range of practical and educational aspects.

Authors choose the smart parking topic, because parking optimization is an actual problem in modern cities. With the growth of population and development of economic, the number of vehicles on the roads is increasing day by day. Parking is becoming one of the major problems for cities, and it makes significant cost position [5], [6]. Because of this, parking is limited in major cities including universities and major attractions all around the globe [7], [8].

Physical model of the real-time smart parking educational system (acronym is EduPark) is built for educational purposes to teach the students different aspects of data collection, using various sensor technologies, to program different development platforms (in authors case it is Arduino) and/or microcontrollers, to test different data transfer scenarios. Virtual system is developed to teach process visualization and simulation, to show how physical systems can be modelled in virtual environment.

1 PHYSICAL REALIZATION OF EDUPARK

Physical realization of EduPark system consists of base table surface where car-parking model is built (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. EduPark physical system

Parking has one entrance and one exit, six parking lots and digital display, which shows number of free parking lots. There are eight HC-SR05 ultrasonic sensors (entrance, exit and each parking lot) connected to Arduino, which are used to identify presence of car. A liquid crystal display (LCD) is used to inform about free (unoccupied) parking lots. Parking schematic view is demonstrated in Fig. 2.:

Fig. 2. Schematic view of the EduPark physical system

1.1 Arduino program

Arduino is used as a main development platform. All ultrasonic sensors are connected to the platform and their status is recorded. As well all sensor status is transmitted to the remote data collection and processing unit (DCPU, see section 3) using wireless communication module ESP8266. Schematic view of the developed Arduino system is demonstrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic view of the developed Arduino system (in Fritzing)

Detection distance of the object (car) is set to 5 cm. Arduino continuously checks for ultrasonic sensor status changes. When such changes occur – data about parking lot event (drive-in / drive-out) is sent to ESP8266 module and information on the LCD is updated. Arduino sends data to ESP8266 using serial communication (UART).

WiFi module ESP8266 creates a secure connection (SSL) with remote DCPU and sends a POST message according to defined API, containing event data received from Arduino: parking element id and event type (in / out).

Example of sent HTTP request:

```
POST /api/parkings/{parkingId}/elements/{elementId}/events HTTP/1.1
Host: parking.science.itf.llu.lv
Content-Type: application/json
```

```
{"type": "DRIVE_IN"}
```

Further data processing is handled by remote DCPU.

1.2 Simplified Arduino program

For parking event simulation and testing simplified Arduino system is developed. Sensors and their operations are substituted by push buttons. Schematic view of the developed Arduino system is demonstrated in Fig. 4:

Fig. 4. Schematic view of the developed simplified Arduino system (in Fritzing)

In this case, user has to push buttons to simulate car entering and exiting parking lots. Led lights change color depending on spot occupancy. This simple system is built to demonstrate, that physical systems and sensors can be replaced by other elements without changing system's functionality and logic. Events from this system are also transferred to previously mentioned remote DCPU.

2 VIRTUAL IMPLEMENTATION OF EDUPARK SYSTEM

Together with physical parking model, also its virtual example is developed to demonstrate, that operation of physical system can be modeled and simulated in virtual environment. Fig. 5 demonstrates system's logical concept and has description of all system elements. User manually can simulate traffic flow at the parking by triggering events via available controls. All simulated events are sent to central DCPU.

Fig. 5. Schematic view of the developed user interface for parking simulation

Virtual EduPark system is build as single page web application using Angular 2 and Bootstrap 4 frameworks. The system mimics behavior of physical parking system. It maintains state (free and occupied lots) of simulated parking, produces similar parking events and transfers them to DCPU via regular API.

In the future, it is planned to extend this virtual parking system by developing traffic flow simulation. Events will be generated automatically according to user-defined parameters: time interval for a new car arriving to the parking, duration of parking, including random deviations of these parameters. It will demonstrate, that physical model can be simulated fully automatically and synthetic data can be generated for data analysis and parking load prediction model development purposes.

3 DATA COLLECTION AND PROCESSING UNIT OF EDUPARK SYSTEM

Parking event data collection and processing unit (DCPU) is built as separate service providing general API for smart parking systems (like described in section 1 or 2).

Back-end module of DCPU provides API for registering parking system metadata, such as name, description, location, car detection technology, parking lots and other element metadata. API is used for parking event receiving from parking systems. Received data is processed according to defined parking rules, which ensure state

consistency. Processing results are available for external systems (e.g. web or mobile applications) via same API.

Back-end module is built using Java technology stack: Spring Boot 1.5 framework as system backbone, MongoDB 3.4 database. Functionality is covered by unit, integration and acceptance tests build using Spock 1.1 framework.

Front-end module provides mobile-ready user interface for parking data visualization.

System shows general information about parking (e.g. description, location), time of last parking event and actual number of free parking lots. System also shows detailed information about parking elements: status of parking entry, exit and each lot (see Fig. 6).

Web system is publicly available at <https://parking.science.itf.llu.lv>.

Fig. 6. Screenshot of the web system

Front-end module is built as single page web application using Angular 2 and Bootstrap 4 frameworks. It uses regular DCPU API for receiving actual data about parking state, which is updated with 1 second interval.

In the future, it is planned to implement additional data analysis features. One of them is control of parking time and billing, which is important for local municipalities and parking service providers. Another is reservation of parking lots, which is convenient for drivers. Third planned feature is advanced parking load reporting and prediction.

4 EDUCATIONAL ASPECT OF EDUPARK

EduPark system can be used to improve engineering educational process. On its basis, complexity of parking problem can be demonstrated. Different sensors for vehicle detection can be studied. To this moment, there are ultrasonic sensors used for vehicle detection, but it is possible to use also other recognition methods, for example inductive sensors. In addition, vehicle recognition can be done by the image processing from video stream.

Students can study Arduino programming basics. In case of need, Arduino can be substituted by any other development platform (for example by Raspberry Pi). On other hand IT tools like databases, web programming, user interface development etc. can be acquired trying to develop and to improve this parking system.

The educational system EduPark is a relatively simple physical parking model, which can be upgraded and improved. In the system sensors can be substituted by buttons, to simulate presence of cars. This approach can be used to test logic of the developed system and give option to manually simulate car flow at the parking. It is possible to add more parking lots, to make more complex parking, divide it into sectors or even create multi-level parking. This will open new possibilities for improving the parking system, like creation of parking guidance system, which will navigate the car driver through the parking.

This system enables also competition of students (making better and faster algorithm, better user interface, better vehicle recognition, etc.) that makes the educational process much more attractive.

This system also can be used as a children playground for playing with toy cars and to see the parking operation. So options for improving and using the EduPark system are limited only by user and target group imagination.

5 SUMMARY

This paper presents authors developed physical mini model of smart parking system. System can be used for educational purposes demonstrating vehicle detection using different methods. Developed system is based on Arduino platform, together with ultrasonic sensors. In addition to physical system also virtual implementation of parking model is developed. This allows to substitute physical parking elements, but maintaining the logical functionality of the system.

Authors chosen Arduino platform can be substituted by other electronic platforms, for example Raspberry Pi. Vehicle detection can be done by other techniques, e.g. image processing.

In authors opinion such interactive way of engineering education is very attractive for students, because they can develop models of real systems without any risk. At the same time during the implementation of such systems all respective stages of real system development are maintained.

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